
**MICROROBOTIC SWARMS AND THEIR ROBOTIC DELIVERY APPLICATIONS
OFFER NEW VENUES FOR GENE THERAPY DELIVERY****Moataz Dowaidar^{1,2}**

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Abstract

Over the past decade, microrobotic swarms and their robotic delivery applications have evolved substantially. This review looked at the current advances in microrobotics swarming, navigation, and localization, as well as their applications for targeted imaging-guided distribution. While a substantial effort has been proposed towards in-vivo controlled administration, several restrictions remain. Research opportunities and challenges are presented, with probable solutions on the horizon. Microrobotic Swarm, Controller and Integration of Imaging Modality. Integrating the swarm controller with in vivo imaging technologies is a requirement for in vivo delivery jobs. Trading between imaging and control systems, as well as developing a swarm control scheme based on current imaging systems, is hard to do. Research should focus on integrating swarm navigation and imaging into the same energy source. The toxicity threshold needed depends on where microrobotic swarms are employed. Before establishing therapeutic procedures, the swarms' biocompatibility and toxicity should be evaluated. Swarms in endovascular delivery applications may require a more complete toxicity evaluation, including a range of parameters such as materials, dose, and block size. Research opportunities include bridging customized therapy/delivery and imaging-guided swarm control.

In the biological world, collective behavior is a regular occurrence. Through communication, hundreds, thousands, or even millions of individual organisms can congregate, and the swarming individuals exhibit diverse types of cooperation. (1–3) Each collected swarm may travel as a single entity and alter form drastically in response to external stimuli or to suit the needs of certain tasks: Ants connect their bodies to construct rafts to withstand floods and carry large-size food in a collecting mode, while honeybee swarms increase collective stability by actively altering their morphology. (4). (5,6) Artificial robotic systems that can on-demand manage their collective behaviors to accomplish coordinated tasks that are difficult to do with a single agent have been inspired by various swarming intelligence and emergent behaviors. (7,8)

Because of the fast advancements in nanotechnology and manufacturing, it is now possible to scale down remotely controlled robots that can execute tasks on demand. Micro/nanorobots, being small-scale devices, can navigate through diverse physiological settings in a controlled way using external power sources, self-propulsion, (1818), and hybrid propulsion. (19–22) More biocompatible and biodegradable micro/nanorobots with various capabilities are now available thanks to recent advances in manufacturing, actuation, and functionalization. (2326) These micro- and nanoscale robots have the potential to be used in a variety of biomedical applications, including targeted delivery, biosensing, micromanipulation, and minimally invasive surgery. (39–41) Micro/nanorobots, on the other hand, face difficulties in carrying out practical applications. Micro/nanorobots have limited imaging and control capabilities due to their small size and volume. In vivo imaging methods have limits in terms of resolution and contrast, which makes real-time imaging and localisation of these tiny micromachines difficult. Microrobots are difficult to operate in dynamic settings like blood arteries due to their tiny driving force. Environmental disturbances impede navigation efficiency, making the application procedure time-consuming. Furthermore, due to its small size and volume, a single micro/nanorobot may not be handled as an effective end effector or drug carrier. Using microrobotic swarms in delivery jobs has several benefits over using individual agents: First, a greater tolerance for the structural and material simplicity of the construction components. When scaling down to the sub-millimeter or micro/nanometer scale, an individual micro/capacity nanorobot may be harmed, but their collective capabilities can be improved. The second benefit is the increased capacity to fulfill delivery duties. Individual micro/nanorobots can not accomplish delivery duties that collective micro/nanorobots can, including handling many objects in a batch, carrying big payloads, and performing concurrent activities. The third benefit is increased adaptation to complicated situations. In in-vivo circumstances, the transformation of a collective pattern allows for improved job performance in restricted, constricted lumens (e.g., blood arteries, bile ducts, pancreatic ducts). Finally, increased medication and material delivery capability. In comparison, because of the size constraint, the amount of drugs/materials that an individual agent may load may reach a critical limit. Fifth, the contrast in several imaging instruments has been improved. The contrast of medical imaging (e.g., ultrasound imaging, magnetic resonance imaging) might be improved by a collected microrobotic swarm, and microswarms made up of mixed/heterogeneous building blocks are appropriate for multi-imaging modalities, indicating significant promise for localized therapy.

Several essential stages need to be studied before deploying microrobotic swarms in practical applications. Pattern creation and control, including collective formation and motion control in various circumstances, are heavily influenced by interactions between building blocks under various energy inputs. The capacity to adapt to diverse surroundings is enabled through collective movement and metamorphosis. To conduct practical applications, pattern localization is necessary, and the imaging system must be compatible with the control system. Finally, image-guided delivery may be created depending on the application site and delivery objects using a fundamental understanding of different forms of microrobotic swarms with the integration of imaging modalities. Recent developments in the collective behavior of external power-driven micro/nanorobots and their applications in imaging-guided distribution are being

reviewed and addressed in order to utilize active-matter swarms from the robotic delivery perspective. The fundamental interactions between building blocks and agent-boundary interactions are described and explored in the context of swarm formation under external fields (i.e., magnetic fields, light, acoustic fields, electric fields). The collective motion and pattern navigation of microrobotic swarms, as well as interactions between the swarm and its surroundings, are next discussed. Swarm localization in different imaging modalities is summarized and contrasted, and the integration of control systems with imaging techniques is explored, in order to localize a swarm in biological and opaque settings. Finally, an overview of research efforts on imaging-guided delivery of swarming micro/nanorobots demonstrates the present state of remotely driven microrobotic swarm delivery. We want to give insights to practitioners interested in bringing external power-driven microrobotic swarms to imaging-guided targeted delivery and localized treatment by emphasizing current work on the collective behaviors of external-power driven micro/nanorobots.

Pattern Formation and Navigation Driven by the Environment

Micro/nanorobot collective behaviors are the outcome of basic interactions between individuals. In various settings, customizable interaction offers a mechanism for swarm formation, navigation, and pattern change. This section begins with an overview of how external fields, such as magnetic fields, light, acoustic fields, and electric fields, affect interactions between micro/nanorobots. Hybrid field interactions (e.g., the combination of magnetic and acoustic fields) are also briefly discussed. The generation and navigation of swarms under various field inputs is then summarized and contrasted.

Microrobotic Swarm with Magnetic Drive

The interactions between magnetic agents, which are magnetized by external magnetic fields, allow for their dynamic development into different patterns. Magnetic agents are ferromagnetic and paramagnetic materials that are significantly impacted by magnetic fields applied to them. The hysteresis demonstrates that ferromagnetic materials (e.g., Fe, Co, Ni) stay magnetized after being magnetized by an external field, according to the magnetization curve of ferromagnetic materials (e.g., Fe, Co, Ni). When a weak magnetic field is applied, the magnetic moments tend to align with the external field. When the external field is removed, the magnetism of paramagnetic materials vanishes. Iron-oxide nanoparticles, for example, are a common substance utilized in microrobotic manipulation and targeted distribution techniques. (84,85) The method for arranging paramagnetic particles into intricate patterns is provided by the tunable interactions between them. Based on their controlling formation methods, we divide magnetic-field-driven microrobotic swarms into three types: magnetic interaction-induced swarm, hydrodynamic interaction-induced swarm, and weakly interacted swarm.

Swarms Caused by Magnetic Interaction

Magnetic agent-agent interactions, which may be regulated by the input magnetic field, dictate the development of magnetic interaction-induced swarms. The induced magnetic moment m of a single magnetic agent and the field gradient B determine the subjected magnetic force F , where the magnetic moment m depends on the materials and volume of the agent, as does the magnetic permeability, where μ_0 is the permeability of free space, and V is the volume of the magnetic materials. Multiple agents are gradually assembled during swarm formation, and each

agent is subjected to a magnetic force from other magnetic agents. (87) The magnetic force between two agents may be simplified into two magnetic dipoles (m_i, m_j , situated at P_i and P_j), where $r_{ij} = P_i - P_j$ and r is the unit vector between the two dipoles. Interactions between agents have been introduced using rotating magnetic fields. $B(t) = B [\cos(2ft)x - \sin(2ft)y]$, where B is the field strength and f is the frequency, is a common in-plane rotating field. The magnetic force between microrobots varies throughout actuation, becoming maximum when m_i, m_j are parallel to r_{ij} and repulsive when the two moments are normal to r_{ij} . The contact develops attraction over time, resulting in the collection of magnetic microrobots. The paramagnetic particles self-assemble into a circular revolving pattern in the presence of a rotating magnetic field. (53) When the external field is removed, the dipole-dipole interactions vanish, resulting in the disassociation of the constructed pattern.

Microrobotic patterns produced by interactions between particle chains have been observed in a precessing magnetic field, in addition to direct interactions between particles. The magnetic attraction between particles forms particle chains, and the swarm is produced by balancing magnetic dipolar attraction and multipolar repulsion between particle chains. The magnetic dipolar interaction is adjusted in part by the precession angle of the input field. The mean interaction between m_i and m_j over a cycle is given as (88), where θ is the precession angle to the spinning axis. The magnetic interaction can be both repulsion ($0^\circ - 54.7^\circ$) and attraction ($54.7^\circ - 90^\circ$). When $\theta = 54.7^\circ$, the dipolar interaction averages to zero (magic angle). It is set between 68 and 72 degrees to achieve particle chain attraction, with the pairwise distance convergent to a dynamically stable range. The dipole-hexapole interaction dominates the repulsive multipolar interaction at 61.5° , resulting in long-range attraction and short-range repulsion. (89) Magnetic building pieces can also be collected into swarm states at the nanoscale scale. The interaction between nanoparticle chains, triggered by an oscillating field, creates a ribbon-like microswarm (Figure 2c). (43,52) The input parameters, such as field intensity, frequency, and field ratio, which is defined as the ratio between alternating and constant fields, influence the magnetic chain-chain interactions. An actuated particle chain is created in a low Reynolds number regime by balancing the primary two torques: magnetic torque m and hydrodynamic drag torque d from viscous fluids. The total magnetic torque exerted on the center of the chain (N particles with radius a) is determined by adding the torques of surrounding particles, where r_i is the distance between the first particle and the center of the chain, and $m_2(t)$ is the induced dipole moment of a particle. The viscous drag of a chain with angular velocity $\omega(t)$ is calculated using the formula (90), where η is the viscosity of the surrounding fluid. The Mason number, which is defined as the ratio of the two torques ($RT = d/m$), is used to calculate chain length. If the RT is less than one, the chain is stabilized by the greater magnetic torque. When you get beyond oneness, the tremendous viscous drag causes fragmentation. The chain length ($L = 2Na$) may be determined by examining a crucial situation in which the two torques balance each other prior to chain fragmentation ($RT = 1$). The nanoparticle chains are dynamically formed, destroyed, and collected during swarm formation, with time-dependent chain-chain interactions. Finally, millions of nanoparticles are arranged in a ribbon-like swarm pattern.

Swarms Caused by Hydrodynamic Interaction

In the formation of microrobotic systems, hydrodynamic contact is crucial. Building block actuation disrupts the surrounding fluid and deforms interfaces (e.g., air-liquid interface, liquid-liquid interface), affecting the collective state and pattern-environment interaction. Hydrodynamic interaction-induced swarms are microrobotic swarms that arise largely as a result of interaction exerted via the medium (e.g., hydrodynamic flow and interface). In a low-Reynolds-number environment, a vortex forms around a spinning nanoparticle chain. It attracts nearby chains across a long distance, shortening the distance between them. Two vortices rotate in the same direction and combine after a certain distance, resulting in the collection of nanoparticles. After achieving an equilibrium condition, a circular pattern is gradually formed. (51) The vortex-based analysis may also be used to investigate the swarm's collective state. Due to the actuation of the external rotating magnetic field, the vorticity in the swarm's core area will not fade. (91) As a result, the vorticity (z) and velocity (u) distributions inside the vortex core become, where Γ is the vortex's circulation and R is the vortex's radius. The vorticity decreases as the distance from the core increases due to fluid viscosity. In the low-Reynolds-number domain, inertia forces are ignored. The vorticity and velocity distributions outside the vortex center become, where ν is the fluid's kinematic viscosity. As a result, the inner interactions between the core area and nanoparticles determine the size of a vortex-like swarm. At the same time, the particle chains rotate around their own axis and orbit the swarm center. Although both are controlled by rotating magnetic fields, a hydrodynamic interaction-induced swarm is quite different from a magnetic interaction-governed swarm. Because of the high magnetic attraction between the construction components, the magnetic interaction-governed swarm behaves like a rolling disk. The velocity distribution may be calculated using the formula $u_i = 2fRc_i$, where Rc_i is the distance between the first particle and the pattern's center. A swarm of helical microrobots is propelled upward by a rotating magnetic field, reaching the upper air-liquid interface and forming a co-rotating swarm pattern. The hydrodynamic effect is dominated by the rotation-translation coupling, in this case, (92), which is comparable to the dynamic self-assembly of spherical particles. (93) The hydrodynamic interactions might be tweaked to alter the collective state. The development of dynamic lattices, rather than a highly concentrated collected state, is the result of significant hydrodynamic repulsion between rotating ferromagnetic microparticle chains. (94) Vortices may also be produced by an alternating magnetic field, with the particle density of the constructed pattern being changed by adjusting the field parameters. (95) The interface is a unique location for swarm development, where capillary contact is important. Microparticles are formed into dynamic atoms at a liquid-liquid interface, driven by an alternating magnetic field. (46) The magnetic repulsion between chains and the resultant hydrodynamic streaming fluxes are both important in the creation of atoms. The chains oscillate in response to the external field on a regular basis, and an excited circular wave causes the creation of radial ordering of chains. The aster-like pattern is created by the distribution of these chains on different slopes of the same wave. The presence of top liquid dramatically alters the interior hydrodynamic interactions and force balance, resulting in a completely different dynamic pattern than swarm formation at the air-liquid interface. Weakly Interacted Swarm (97)

If the interactions between agents are insufficient to impact one another's mobility, each agent in a microswarm moves autonomously. The swarm was classified as a weakly interacting

swarm. In the vitreous humor, a collection of helical microrobots controlled by a rotating magnetic field demonstrates movement. (69) The magnetic and hydrodynamic interactions between microrobots are insufficient to impact the motion behavior of nearby robots due to the large separation distance between them. The robots move at their own pace, eventually approaching the retina. The surface coating can alter the mobility of a collection of helical microrobots. (86) Robots with various coatings (hydrophobic and hydrophilic) move at the same velocity ratio when actuated by a rotating field below the step-out frequency. By raising the frequency above the step-out frequency, they display distinct locomotor characteristics, allowing for selective control of robots with varied surface coatings. To improve mass transfer, a set of magnetic rods travels independently toward the fluid-clot interface. (67) Collective nanorods can boost the rate of tissue plasminogen activator (tPA)-mediated thrombolysis by up to 2-fold, indicating that collective small agents can improve individual functioning.

Swarm Navigation in the Presence of a Magnetic Field

The use of controlled swarm movement to accomplish targeted navigation and materials distribution is being studied. Because the drag coefficient rises as an item approaches a wall, one of the swarm locomotion techniques focuses on actuation at a boundary (e.g., substrate and sidewall). (98) The force asymmetry caused by differing hydrodynamic interactions between various sections of swarming organisms and a barrier causes movement. (99) Rotating nanoparticles in the XZ-plane are hydrodynamically linked to the substrate by a rotating magnetic field, converting rotation to translational motion. The attractive dipolar interactions produced by the field along the Y-directions prevent particle separation during locomotion, and the whole swarm pattern may be operated as a single entity. A spinning particle swarm might migrate toward the channel wall utilizing an acoustic field-induced radiation force to achieve this motion. (53) Aside from particle rotation, all particles orbit the pattern's center. As a result, the rotation of the whole pattern causes the motion symmetry to be broken, resulting in translational motion. The movement of building pieces may have an impact on their immediate surroundings. The motion of the chain is caused by the fluidic imbalance between the two chain ends. Meanwhile, the fluids from other preceding chains have the greatest impact on the pairwise motion of the chains. Locomotion might be produced in two-dimensional (2D) swarm patterns under in-plane dynamic fields by introducing an out-of-plane static field component. The translational motion of chains is caused by the rotating/oscillating plane of nanoparticle chains inside a swarm tilting at a tiny angle (pitch angle) to the substrate. At the same time, the magnetic and hydrodynamic interactions between chains allow for controlled pattern navigation.

Swarm navigation is possible by disrupting the symmetry of pattern-induced flow, in addition to boundary-assisted locomotion. The balance between magnetic interactions and chain-induced flows determines the form of an axi-symmetric aster. As a result, the flow is symmetric, and there is little movement. An in-plane static magnetic field has been used to break the hydrodynamic symmetry. The axial symmetry of hydrodynamic flow is broken as the pattern opens, and the pattern locomotion is controlled by the direction of the in-plane field. The in-plane field strength influences the motion velocity, resulting in several opening stages. With increased field strength (0–10 Oe), the pattern deformation increases, resulting in a faster actuation velocity. Due to the fully open pattern (10–22 Oe), the flow becomes symmetric, and the velocity eventually drops to zero. To disrupt the symmetry of flow in a non-axisymmetric

swarm pattern, a nonmagnetic bead is put on one side of the swarm pattern. (47) This method might also give us a swarm pattern of movement. The motion direction, on the other hand, is difficult to regulate. The motion of construction pieces is used to navigate a weakly interacting swarm. Helical microrobots move by producing nonreciprocal motion in the presence of rotating magnetic fields. Helical microrobots have the benefit of not requiring boundary constraints for locomotion and allowing for three-dimensional (3D) mobility. The number of helical microrobots in a group has a big impact on the collective state. A greater concentration causes stronger interactions between the particles, resulting in a dynamically stable pattern. Inside the swarm, magnetic assembly may also occur. (100) The comparatively low helix concentration, on the other hand, demonstrates autonomous motion. A magnetic field gradient can be used to drive movement in building blocks that lack propulsion or controlled actuation direction, such as a swarm of rotating nanorods.

Microrobotic Swarm Powered by Light

Photoresponsive agents have been driven by light, which allows for wireless and distant propagation with adjustable radiation energy. Photoactive materials are used in light-driven building blocks to introduce interactions between agents. Around photoactive materials like AgCl and TiO₂ particles, as well as TiO₂/Pt and TiO₂/Au Janus particles, light causes a solute concentration gradient in a specific direction.

Building blocks that are homogeneous

Because of the asymmetric photodecomposition, 1 μ m-diameter AgCl particles in DI water move at velocities of up to 100 μ m/s when exposed to UV light. (73) Because of the asymmetric pace, an electrolyte gradient forms around the particle, resulting in self-diffusiophoresis, which is similar to diffusiophoretic particle movement. The generation of H⁺ and Cl⁻ produces an electrolyte gradient, which causes AgCl particles to move. The particles progressively collected, but owing to short-range repulsive electrostatic interactions, physical contact between particles was prevented. The long-range attractive diffusiophoretic interaction is examined experimentally by introducing SiO₂ particles into the solution, where the passive SiO₂ particles are gathered and surround the AgCl particles, mimicking predator-prey behavior. Janus particles are unique particles with two or more distinct physical characteristics on their surfaces. Their asymmetric structure, or functionalization, allows for actuation and collective activity in the presence of external fields. Propulsion of graphite/SiO₂ Janus microparticles in a water-2,6-lutidine combination using laser light (wavelength of 532 nm). (101) The light is absorbed by the carbon-coated hemisphere, and local demixing occurs as a result of the heating action, with the demixing-induced physical force propelling the particles. Clusters develop at low particle densities in this quasi-2D suspension, and at higher densities, a phase transition into giant clusters and a dilute gas phase occurs. Particles are prevented from having a head-on collision due to the persistence of their orientations, resulting in a cluster formation. With a faster actuation speed, the likelihood of the cluster colliding with additional particles rises, resulting in a bigger cluster size. Controlling UV light demonstrates the reversible gathering-spreading behavior of a set of SiO₂/TiO₂ Janus particles. (102) A system made up of pure SiO₂ and TiO₂ particles exhibits similar characteristics, with SiO₂ components acting as surface pumps repelling TiO₂ particles. However, navigating these swarming colloidal patterns in a regulated manner is difficult. The motion velocity (U) of a

particle in a monovalent salt solution (concentration gradient: c) is given by (104), where D_c and D_a are the cation and anion diffusion coefficients, c_0 is the bulk ion concentration, e is the charge of an electron, k_B is the Boltzmann constant, T is the absolute temperature, and ϵ is the dielectric permittivity of the sol. According to the preceding study, controlling the motion direction of a self-diffusiophoresis particle is difficult. Swarm navigation is aided by the use of a patterned substrate and a changing light spot (source). Sagués et al. show that using a functionalized substrate allows a light-driven swarm to form and navigate in a controlled manner. (76) Under UV and blue light irradiation, the photosensitive azosilane monolayer assumes a *cis* (planar) structure and then reverts to a *trans* (homeotropic) configuration. Aster and vortex-like swarm patterns of polystyrene (PS) microparticles form between a photosensitive and a nonphotosensitive plate in the presence of an alternating electric field. Because of the switchable *trans* and *cis* isomers, the transition between the two patterns is accomplished by altering the radiation type (UV, blue light). Swarms may be navigated in two ways: by altering the location of the light spot or by moving the irradiated region along a predetermined path. The particles migrate to the new site in a leader-follower fashion, rather than as a tightly coupled ensemble.

Swarm navigation may also be accomplished by programming the light radiation, in addition to changing the light spot position. (72) In a spreading condition, when UV is supplied sideways, TiO_2 particles move phototactically toward the same locomotion direction. When the light is turned off, the motion ceases and becomes random Brownian movements. The particles are then dispersed and move away from the light source, forming a circular pattern that is centered in a new location. As a result, a pulsed UV light with on-off repeating cycles may be utilized to activate the swarm in spreading-regathering stages in a straight line. By irradiating UV from distinct side directions, the pattern shows dilatation-gathering behaviors with a moving center toward either the X or Y directions. Deng et al. hypothesized that, in addition to UV-driven collective motion, near-infrared (NIR) light-induced convection flow can promote swarm formation and navigation. (103) As the temperature of the NIR-exposed liquid medium rises, a convection flow develops between the exposed and unexposed areas. In such a flow, TiO_2/Pt microparticles are subjected to drag forces and move toward the center of the exposed region. Electrostatic attraction and diffusiophoretic repulsive interactions between microparticles control swarm formation. By following the exposed region, positive phototactic behavior was used to traverse the swarm pattern. The collective states of silica microparticle swarms are likewise affected by the UV source's motion speed. If the source's speed falls below a certain point, the microparticles follow the UV spot at a steady speed. Due to the varied reactions of microparticles with differing components and sizes, this approach might be used to separate particles from a mixed ensemble.

Heterogeneous Building Blocks are a type of heterogeneous building block that can be used. Light-driven hierarchical microswarms made up of several sorts of building pieces show multiresponsiveness and the ability to create coordinated micromachines. Leader-follower-like swarm patterns are created by dielectric microparticles of various sizes and dielectric characteristics regulated by electrohydrodynamic (EHD) fluxes, which are triggered by an AC electric field. (71) Switchable phototaxis is seen in microswarms produced by large (2 μm in diameter) and tiny (0.5 μm in diameter) TiO_2 microparticles, i.e., negative and positive phototaxis with low (4 mW/cm^2) and high (500 mW/cm^2) sidewise UV intensity, respectively.

Under UV light, non-electrolyte self-diffusiophoresis causes negative phototaxis in the microparticles. (106) The asymmetric photocatalytic reactions on the surface of particles enable the swarm pattern to migrate away from the light source when the UV intensity is low. The bigger particle has a faster phototactic velocity and so becomes the pattern's leader. The collected tiny particles have a higher phototactic velocity when the light intensity is increased. The EHD flows stabilize the whole pattern, which tends to coincide with the light direction. As a result, changing the light direction may be used to conduct swarm navigation. Forming a pattern with different particles demonstrates the various collective photoresponses. Due to the minimal UV response, the little SiO₂ particles follow the big TiO₂ particles under vertically transmitted UV light. Because of interparticle diffusiophoretic repulsions, the pattern becomes symmetric by altering the diameter of the two particles. The motion was controlled by turning on and off the UV light, and by administering UV irradiation, the two patterns were shown to have opposing phototaxis.

Microrobotic Swarm Driven by Acoustic Field

The use of acoustic waves to control small agents on the micrometer/nanometer scale allows for a wireless, noncontact approach to microrobotic actuation and micromanipulation. (109,110) Acoustic waves are typically created by piezoelectric transducers, according to current research. The acoustic radiation force acts on micrometer-scale particles in the acoustic field. (111) Because the force on objects in standing waves is significantly greater than that in moving waves, most current research focuses on standing acoustic wave-driven actuation and micromanipulation. (112) An object's acoustic force may be represented as (113) N where p_0 and V are the object's pressure amplitude and volume, and k is the wavelength and wavenumber, and d is the particle's distance from the node or antinode. ρ represents the relationship between the object and the medium's density and compressibility, as $(5c - 2w)/(2c + 2w) - c/w$, where c and w are the object and medium's density, and c and w are the object and medium's compressibility, respectively. Because the acoustic force is related to the size of objects, items with sizes smaller than the wavelength are difficult to manage.

Under the influence of acoustic waves, Au-Ru microrods levitated to the middle plane. The microrods display switchable gathering and random motions in the nodal plane, where ultrasound creates a standing wave, resulting in a dispersed state with a ring-like pattern. (107) The individual rods spin at a kilohertz frequency around the chain axis and travel along the chain at the same time. The swarm pattern dissolved once the acoustic power was turned off, and the microrods moved on a disordered course. Pt-Au nanowires in a hydrogen peroxide solution also exhibited reversible collective behaviour. (79) Electrophoretic propulsion-induced spreading is demonstrated by the catalytic nanowires' independent mobility in the solution. The acoustic field's standing waves allow for the creation of a high-density pattern. Meanwhile, the Pt-Au nanowires are being pushed into the low-pressure area by the pressure gradient. The acoustic force is split into two types: primary and secondary radiation forces, the latter of which is generated by acoustic waves rescattered by nanowires and rises as the interagent distance decreases. The horizontal component of the main radiation force and the secondary radiation force are principally responsible for the creation of circular nanowire patterns. The secondary radiation force can cause either attraction or repulsion between agents. As a result, turning on and off the ultrasound may regulate the collecting and spreading of nanowires. Changing the position of pressure nodes, which is performed by altering the

acoustic frequency, allows the swarm pattern to move. At a pace of about 45 m/s, the swarm pattern travels to a new location. Meanwhile, due to the secondary radiation force, the swarm pattern retains its circular form. However, navigating the swarm pattern along a predetermined path is difficult since low-pressure areas are difficult to create simply by altering the input frequency. In the formation of a microswarm of liquid metal agents, the acoustic-gathering effect is also observed. At a frequency of 730 kHz, EGaln nanorod stripes develop. By increasing the frequency to 728 kHz, the stripes eventually blended into bigger stripes, forming a dandelion-like pattern. (78) Finally, by lowering the frequency to 680 kHz, the swarm pattern is dispersed. The distribution of main acoustic radiation forces generated by standing waves is represented by the sound pressure field patterns, which fluctuate with the input frequency. The force along the acoustic energy gradient is applied to nanorods in the node plane, resulting in various mobile frequency-dependent patterns.

Microrobotic Swarm Powered by an Electric Field

Based on electrostatic force-based interactions and field-induced EHD interactions between the building pieces, we divide electric field-driven microrobotic swarms into two kinds. The charges of agents, as well as the distance between them, define the attractive or repulsive forces, with the latter force being provided by induced EHD flows. Electrostatic imbalance in the building blocks offers essential mechanisms for diverse collective behaviors in order to create an electrostatic force-induced microswarm. Yan et al. proposed changing the frequency of the input electric field to control the collective states of Janus particles. (82) In the two hemispheres, that is, silica spheres with one hemisphere covered with metal, the local field-induced ionic fluxes at the particle surface have distinct magnitudes. In the gas state, these Janus particles display self-propulsion due to charge-induced electrophoresis. (116) Particles travel in an isotropic manner due to weak dipolar interactions and significant ionic screening effects. (117) With a higher frequency input, the larger dipolar contacts affect collective behavior, where the repulsion between the metallic hemispheres dominates pattern formation (swarm state). The opposing dipoles of the two hemispheres (metallic and dielectric) provide attractive interactions between particles when the input frequency is increased, analogous to particle chain creation in a magnetic field-driven system (active chain state). (118) In addition to adjusting the frequency-dependent dipolar interactions, the clustering of particles is accomplished by adding salt to the solution (cluster phase). Under the influence of an electric field, the polarization of particles with geometric asymmetry produces a variety of collective states. Chiral and achiral structures are formed by colloidal dimers with various geometric ratios, which are regulated by in-plane dipolar repulsion between petals and out-of-plane attraction between the center dimer and surrounding petals. (108) The assembled structure might be affected by the number of dimers as well as the lobe radius ratio. Achiral structures with more than five dimers are more frequent, while chiral structures have four or fewer petals. When the radius ratio approaches 0 or one, the chirality vanishes. The combined structures' rotating propulsion is based on an imbalanced hydrodynamic flow caused by the clusters' chirality.

The induced directional EHD flows surrounding particles, which are driven by an AC electric field, lead to the self-assembly process. Yeh and colleagues demonstrated how to make ordered colloidal aggregates using an EHD-driven assembly method. (119) The flow velocity around a dielectric particle of radius R and polarization coefficient K is given by (120), where $C = 0$

($E_p/2H$). $2H$, where H is the distance between electrodes, E_p and frequency are the amplitude and frequency, ϵ_0 and viscosity of the medium are permittivity and viscosity, and r is the distance between the particle and the impacted region. According to the results of the preceding research, UEHD is significantly influenced by particle kinds, implying that mixing various particles might result in imbalanced EHD flows and particle propulsion. Guan et al. used microparticles of various sizes and dielectric characteristics to create hierarchical microswarms driven by an electric field. (71) Due to the symmetric EHD flow, particles with the same size and dielectric characteristics prefer to combine with each other, but formed clusters exhibit no propulsion. By introducing additional particles with differing sizes or dielectric characteristics into the system, the symmetry can be violated, resulting in net propulsion of the newly created microswarm. The swarm absorbs additional particles by EHD attraction and moves in a coordinated manner during movement. Hydrodynamic interactions between agents can also be introduced by electric fields. The charge distribution on the particle surface is disturbed by applying an electric field to insulating particles inside a conducting fluid. (81) The electrostatic torque causes the particles to rotate in random directions, resulting in a variety of collective states. The rolling particles exhibit various rotation orientations at the same speed at low concentrations, producing an isotropic gaseous phase. By raising the particle fraction over a threshold value that is independent of the particle velocity and the amplitude of the external field, a macroscopic band develops and propagates through an isotropic phase at a constant velocity. By raising the particle fraction further, a homogenous polar-liquid phase is seen, in which the propagating bands' heads catch up with their tails. These findings indicate that hydrodynamic interactions allow individual particles to move in a coordinated manner.

Microrobotic Swarm Driven by Hybrid External Fields

Hybrid field-driven microrobotic swarms are microrobotic swarms that respond to dual inputs and are controlled by hybrid external powers. They could adapt to more complicated surroundings if they had greater control. Depending on the job requirements and application location, the hybrid power-enabled control approach generally comprises of one external power to induce interactions for pattern creation and another external power for pattern navigation or transformation. The hybrid field-actuated microrobotic swarms have exhibited switchable collective behaviors when combined with magnetic and acoustic fields. (121) Controlling the field input demonstrates three forms of collective states of nanorods: spinning pattern, translational motion, and gathering without a stable pattern under the hybrid field, magnetic field, and acoustic field, respectively. The gathering behavior caused by sonic fields may be studied using a similar technique. (79)

Both the attractive interactions between nanorods and the driving torque for pattern rotation are provided by the spinning magnetic field. As a result, the swarm pattern is governed by the interaction between magnetic and acoustic forces. At the border of an equilibrium swarm, the magnetic and acoustic forces are equal, resulting in a circular pattern swarm. The secondary radiation force is responsible for the additional gathering effect. The hybrid actuation techniques' switchable and reversible characteristics suggest that they might give new swarm patterns and navigation approaches that could enhance targeted distribution in various settings. Under rotating magnetic fields, a rotating swarm of magnetic microparticles forms, and the acoustic radiation force on the swarm migrates the particles to the boundary, according to Ahmed et al. (53) The border allows the pattern to travel along the boundary when it transitions

from rotation to translation. Drifting motion is caused by poor contact between the microparticles and the wall, and a tiny (10 Vpp) acoustic force is difficult to impact the entire pattern. A greater translational velocity is obtained by increasing the swarm-boundary contact (20 Vpp) and the rotational frequency input. Such hybrid actuation systems may be appropriate for motion in the vascular system, where delivery duties may be regulated.

Acoustic power combined with light illumination has been used to induce collective behaviors in Janus microrobots in addition to the magnetic-acoustic hybrid control approach. (122) The acoustic field causes the bowl-like TiO₂/Au microrobot to move toward its exterior side, which is produced by the second-order acoustic streaming flow generated by the oscillating edges. As a result, this motion is unaffected by the materials (position of the TiO₂ and Au layers). Unlike acoustic motion, UV light-powered self-propelled motion is material-dependent, meaning that the microrobot moves toward the TiO₂ side. Two groups of Janus microrobots are drawn to the low-pressure nodes by the acoustic pressure gradient, with the external side towards the pattern's center. When the UV light is turned on, the two patterns of Janus microrobots with reversed TiO₂ and Au layers exhibit distinct behaviors: pattern extension and pattern contraction with the Au and TiO₂ outer layers, respectively. Furthermore, the UV light may be turned on and off to regulate this optically modulated collection. Palacci and colleagues have developed hybrid light/magnetic-controlled collective behavior. (75) A portion of the hematite cube is exposed to hydrogen peroxide within the polymer microrobot. Chemical concentration gradients with osmotic and phoretic effects are formed under blue light owing to the breakdown of H₂O₂. These microrobots grow into crystallite formations over time. Thermal diffusion caused the crystallite formations to disintegrate in the absence of light irradiation. Because the alignment of the hematite cube tilts the orientation of the microrobots, the rotational diffusion is prevented by adding a static field (strength: 1 mT). The crystallite structure remains stable and displays motility in the field direction, thanks to the hybrid light/magnetic power. The pattern disintegrated under the magnetic field's influence and will reassemble when the light is turned on. If the initial separation distance is greater than the critical value, the microrobots move independently in the magnetic field direction without establishing a pattern.

Building blocks' magnetic moments have been combined with other external forces to induce collective behavior. Without the need for an external magnetic field, the magnetic interactions between the Ni segments regulate the assembly of the Au-Ru-Ni nanorods. (80) The assembly mode is triggered by the hybrid acoustic/magnetic actuation and behaves like a structure with flexible hinges. The direction of movement is affected by such structural alterations, resulting in a loop-like motion trajectory. Under the irradiation of blue light, peanut-shaped hematite particles cluster as ribbons in the H₂O₂ solution, which is produced by numerous collisions between them. (123) Due to the intrinsic magnetic moments, the ribbon is further stabilized by the magnetic attraction between particles. These two experiments demonstrate how intrinsic moments may be used to aid pattern development and even modify collective motion modes. Cui et al. recently discovered that a series of magnetization processes may control the remanent magnetization of nanomagnets. (125) Complex behaviors can be achieved by assembling modular components with encoded magnetization. This technique allows for the creation of building blocks with programmable magnetization, particularly for those with structural anisotropy. Under the magnetic field-hybrid control technique, microrobotic swarms made up

of these "smart agents" may gain more controllability and sophisticated behaviors, as well as improved adaptation to difficult surroundings.

Swarm Transformation in the Presence of Various Driven Fields

When performing navigation in restricted settings, swarm transformation is crucial. It improves the capacity to adapt and reconfigure formations in tight, limited spaces. By changing the input field, you may fine-tune the interactions between the building blocks or the interactions between the agent and the medium. According to Yu et al., the rotating field's input frequency has a substantial impact on the collective state of a nanoparticle swarm. (51) Particle chains inside the vortex-like microswarm display a step-out pattern with decreasing vortex inward forces when the frequency is increased over a threshold point. As a result, the pattern becomes insecure and exhibits a spreading condition. This state may be used to get several microswarms to interact with one another. Insufficient contact is difficult to drive the merger process due to the relatively vast distance between the two swarms. In the spreading stage, a connecting band forms over time, forcing swarms to communicate with one another. Finally, the field frequency is reduced to maintain a steady inward force, resulting in the formation of a new vortex-like swarm. Furthermore, the pattern change is reversible. Under an elliptically rotating field, the swarm elongates. As a result of the unstable inward push, the pattern splits, resulting in a splitting process and the development of two swarms. The collective state of a hydrodynamic interaction-induced swarm may be adjusted by changing the inner medium-based interactions, according to this research. Changing the magnetic interactions between construction pieces may also be used to alter field-induced swarms. As $B = B_x \sin(2\pi t) \hat{x} - B_y \sin(2\pi t) \hat{y}$, a ribbon-like swarm forms under an oscillating field that is overlaid by an in-plane constant field and an alternating field. (43)

The torque balance-based approach is used to determine the time-dependent lengths of nanoparticle chains after they have been created (6). The magnetic attraction between chains causes nanoparticle chains to dynamically break and rejoin, resulting in pattern creation. The field ratio, defined as the ratio between the two field strengths ($= B_x/B_y$), may be tuned to alter the inner magnetic interaction. The reversible elongation and contraction of the swarm pattern is caused by the dynamic breakdown and reconfiguration of particle chains. A link is formed by concurrently elongating the two microswarms and coordinating their direction, and a new microswarm is detected following the merging process. Inducing magnetic repulsion between chains initiates the splitting process, which causes the pattern to grow to a wider coverage area. A controlled pattern transformation enables an improved swarm control technique. The microswarm may elongate, divide, and reassemble into many subswarms to reach different branches while navigating through a confined channel. Furthermore, conductive construction blocks may be used for swarm transformation. The Au coating on the particle surface acts as a biomimicking structure, forming a conductive microswarm capable of repairing and connecting microcircuits. (52)

The study of pattern transformation in magnetic and hydrodynamic interaction-based microswarms. Different dynamic fields are used to control the interactions between magnetic microparticles, resulting in liquid, chain, vortex, and ribbon collective states. (57) The collective states are governed by magnetic and hydrodynamic interactions. The particles resist each other owing to magnetic repulsion when a vertically oscillating field is supplied ($B(t) = B \sin(\omega t) \hat{z}$). After switching to a rotating field in the XZ-plane, particle chains form due to

magnetic and hydrodynamic attraction between particles ($B(t) = B[(t) \times - \sin(t)]$). A similar process is used to generate a vortex-like swarm in an in-plane rotating field ($B(t) = B[(t) \times - \sin(t)]$). (51) The collective behavior changes to a ribbon-like state when the input field transforms to a preceding field ($B(t) = B_{xx} + B_i [\cos(t) - \sin(t)]$). This type of pattern modification is advantageous for collective manipulation in a variety of tight situations, as well as for distribution over many channels. The pattern transformation is also influenced by the boundary: In a constricted channel, two vortex swarms are likely to combine into a new microswarm. Many ribbons are susceptible to flowing from their neighbors due to the decreasing separation distance. This type of boundary-assisted transformation is known as a passive transformation. Sitti et al. show how to switch between active and passive pattern modification with a switchable control method. (42)

Programming the external magnetic potential energy, or arranging the assembly of modular permanent magnets, controls the active transformation of a pattern. Multiple driven patterned magnets working together allow for pattern reconfiguration, transformation, and switchable constructions of various forms. When navigating in a restricted channel, the swarm's passive transformation is induced by direct contact with the channel's border. The pattern is stabilized by strong agent-agent contact (inner modular repulsion), which also allows for the swarm's great flexibility. During navigation, the swarm adapts its formation morphology in response to environmental limits, acting as a soft-body micro robot. The light-driven microswarm has demonstrated the ability to change in a passive manner. (72) When the TiO_2 particle swarm approaches the narrower channel's entrance, some of the particles fall into the channel, and the swarm elongates to match the channel's limits toward the exit. In a confined context, this swarm navigation with pattern transformation was used to move a SiO_2 payload.

Imaging-Guided Delivery and Swarm Localization

Before undertaking targeted navigation or delivery applications, swarm localization should be considered. Various imaging modalities have been used for image-guided navigation thanks to the advancement of imaging methods (126). Medical imaging-based technologies, such as magnetic resonance imaging (MRI), ultrasound imaging, and positron emission tomography (PET), show promise in the localization and tracking of microrobotic swarms (PET). These well-established methods are extensively utilized in hospitals and clinics, and they may be seamlessly linked with microrobotic control systems. Ultrasound imaging is a well-known, radiation-free medical imaging technology that is frequently utilized. It has been used in clinical diagnostics in the domains of obstetrics and gynecology, cardiology, ophthalmology, and orthopedics, such as assessing blood flow and monitoring the fetus in the uterus. (136–139) The imaging process is based on the interaction of reflected acoustic waves with the imaging objects and their surroundings. Ultrasound imaging has a higher temporal resolution (rapid imaging speed) than other medical imaging methods (e.g., MRI and CT), which is critical for obtaining real-time feedback on moving small-scale objects. Ultrasound pictures may be used to provide real-time feedback control of microrobots for targeted distribution and localized treatment, closing the autonomous control loop. (140) Furthermore, the numerous imaging modes (e.g., B-mode, Doppler mode) allow microrobots to execute required tasks in a variety of settings. According to recent research by Wang et al., the ultrasound contrast is affected by a dynamic microswarm and is reliant on the angle between the nanoparticle chains within and the ultrasonic wave propagation direction. (134) The number of backscattered waves achieves

its greatest value, and the best contrast is exhibited when the angle approaches $90^\circ (= 0^\circ)$, that is, when the chain orients perpendicular to the ultrasonic propagation.

The inner spinning chains of the microswarm, which are driven by a rotating magnetic field, impact the imaging contrast, and dynamic contrast may be seen. Furthermore, the gathering action increases the density of nanoparticles in the swarm zone, resulting in improved imaging contrast. The improved imaging contrast enables deep-tissue microswarm localization, but the nanoparticle dosage must be reduced.(50) The microswarm was monitored in real time using an image differencing-based method, which took advantage of the dynamic contrast and rapid imaging speed. Background sounds are suppressed substantially, and the microswarm is guided along a predetermined course in a viscous environment. These findings show that ultrasonic imaging of a microswarm differs significantly from that of individual microrobots. Ultrasound imaging-guided collective spreading of nanoparticles has also been described, in addition to the administration of nanoparticles in a gathering state. In a fluidic environment, a 3D dynamic magnetic field is used to deconstruct and distribute nanoparticle clusters or huge chains. The cluster is disassembled by increasing the viscous drag on it, and nanoparticle dispersion is controlled via induced dipole-dipole magnetic repulsion. Under the supervision of ultrasound imaging, the spreading technique is verified on the surface of a pig bladder *ex vivo*. (118) The influence of the micrometer-scale irregularity on the inner surface of the organ is minimal as these nanoparticles eventually spread toward a broad coverage area. To bring nanoparticles together, a magnetic needle is pushed into a circular path. Because of the dynamic angle between wave propagation and chain orientation, dynamic ultrasound imaging contrast is produced during both the spreading and regathering processes. As a result, identifying the region with dynamic contrast from the noisy backdrop may be used to calculate the coverage area of nanoparticles.

The use of ultrasound imaging to guide swarm navigation in an *ex vivo* bovine eyeball was demonstrated.

(60) Mesh-like structures in the vitreous humor influence the development and navigation of microswarms. The forces created by the rotating swarm are capable of pushing and twisting the meshes during navigation, according to experimental data, and the propulsion force derived from Stokes' law and Weissenberg number is predicted to be in the range of 1–8 N. The microswarm is created and guided to follow a right-angled route at an average velocity of 200 m/s under ultrasound imaging feedback, with the beginning position of the swarm established by monitoring the nanoparticle injection (tip of a syringe needle). Aside from biofluid navigation, an ultrasound-guided swarm has been used to aid in the destruction of blood clots. Under the influence of an oscillating magnetic field, a ribbon-like nanoparticle swarm can develop in the blood of rats. (61) In a viscous fluid with complex components, swarm formation is enabled by time-dependent attractive interactions among particles. Adding a tilt angle (pitch angle) to the field component allows the microswarm to move around: By adding the angle to the alternating component and the constant component, the microswarm shows translational motion along the long (L-mode) and short (S-mode) axes, respectively. With the S-mode and L-mode, the velocity may reach up to 26 m/s and 35 m/s, respectively.

The microswarm is transformed by changing the field ratio, which causes the particle chains to disintegrate and regrade, resulting in a reversible pattern of elongation. The direction of particle chains influences ultrasound imaging contrast, and the resulting dynamic contrast allows the

microswarm to be tracked against a noisy backdrop. In a constrained context, the multimode steerability and transformation capability enable adaptive pattern navigation. The microswarm is guided in L-mode toward a blood clot using ultrasound imaging. It subsequently went into S-mode and was extended in order to adapt to the clot area. The tissue plasminogen activator-mediated lysis rate increases 2.5-fold under the impact of swarm-induced 3D blood flow compared to lysis without the microswarm. Furthermore, by observing the microswarm under real-time feedback, the lysis process may be indirectly tracked.

Ultrasound Doppler imaging, unlike B-mode imaging, depends on the Doppler effect, which involves detecting frequency changes in reflected ultrasonic waves caused by object motion. A moving reflector travels a small distance between two pulses in a time interval equal to the reciprocal of the pulse repetition frequency, creating a frequency difference between the two echoes. A novel Doppler curve with a Doppler shift of $f_d = 2(v/c) f_0$ was produced by generating numerous pulses, where c is the propagation speed of waves in the medium, f_0 is the emitted frequency, and v is the reflector's motion speed. Doppler imaging is a technique for detecting blood flow velocity that is frequently utilized. Sitti and colleagues recently showed that a collection of hairbots can follow ultrasonic signals in tissue. (135) Hairbots are made by injecting paramagnetic nanoparticles into a piece of hair to create magnetically sensitive, biocompatible constructs. The hairbot's hollow medullary cavity improves ultrasonography contrast and aids tracking in B-mode imaging. Color Doppler imaging is used to monitor moving hairbots in chicken tissue, with the exhibited color representing movement. The tissue's Doppler color aids researchers in distinguishing the swarm from the background tissue. Magnetic excitation and ultrasound Doppler imaging, also known as magnetomotive ultrasound (MMUS), is a relatively recent imaging method based on magnetic excitation and ultrasonic Doppler. (141) The magnetic agents inside the imaging zone are excited by a dynamic magnetic field, while an ultrasonic probe scans the area at the same time. The backscattered ultrasound waves are phase shifted by the moving agents, and the acoustic data is captured by the probe and processed by algorithms. (142) A swarm of magnetic nanoparticles was studied using MMUS imaging. (133) In a tissue-mimicking phantom, imaging findings from B-mode imaging, common MMUS, and inverse MMUS are compared. In contrast to B-mode imaging, it is difficult to quantify the particle dispersion in an MMUS picture since the observed motion is dependent on both the magnetic response and nanoparticle concentration. Temporal resolution is one of the most difficult aspects of MMUS-based swarm localisation. Currently, popular methods take about 5 seconds to create a single clear picture, which might impair the accuracy with which a mobile microswarm can be located. (143)

Optical coherence tomography (OCT) is a high-resolution noncontact imaging method. Because OCT offers a quantitative evaluation of retinal layers, it is frequently used in ophthalmology to identify glaucoma and retinal disorders. (144) The concepts of OCT are similar to those of medical ultrasonography imaging: Near-infrared light is directed toward tissue. The delay of the backscattered waves is used to determine the depth of tissue. A swarm of helical microrobots has been observed near to the retina of cows' eyes using clinical OCT. (69) Individual microrobot monitoring is difficult due to the tiny size of the microrobots and the resolution restriction. The swarm of robots increases the contrast with the OCT, and the dispersion of the swarm can also be seen. The geographic distribution of these microrobots near

the retina is quantified using a 3D reconstruction method. The low penetration depth of OCT, on the other hand, restricts swarm localisation and delivery in deep-tissue areas.

Fluorescent imaging methods for tissue samples and cells are frequently utilized in biological research since they do not produce detrimental ionizing effects. (145) Cells and organelles have been labeled using a variety of fluorescent probes, including organic dyes, quantum dots, and fluorescent metal-organic frameworks. (146–148) Various building blocks are created by adding fluorescent substances, primarily inherently fluorescent materials for manufacturing and functionalized agents with fluorescent probes, to form a fluorescent-trackable microrobotic swarm. Felfoul et al. suggest using a swarm of fluorescent magnetotactic bacteria (*Magnetococcus marinus* strain MC-1) to navigate through tumor areas. (65) Without a magnetic field, cells orient randomly or swim toward low-oxygen concentrations due to thermal force-induced Brownian motion. The magnetosome (a membranous chain of Fe₃O₄ nanoparticles) inside MC-1 generates magnetic torque to force motion along the magnetic field direction in the presence of a directional magnetic field. As a result, the MC-1's magnetotaxis enables swarm navigation in the tumor area and drug-loaded nanoliposome delivery into hypoxic tumor regions. According to the findings of the experiments, up to 55% of MC-1 cells enter the hypoxic areas of the tumor, indicating that active penetration is better than passive delivery. The findings suggest that swarming bioagents or biohybrid agents have the potential to offer tailored, high-steerability delivery, potentially addressing problems with artificial swarming systems. In vivo imaging systems based on fluorescence have been developed to track swarm navigation and delivery. Due to the low photon absorption of endogenous biomolecules, this method allows for a better signal-to-background ratio and deeper tissue penetration when imaging agents. The surface functionalization of artificial bacterial flagella (ABFs) with fluorescent probes, as described by Servant et al., permits fluorescence imaging of their bodies. (44)

A swarm of ABFs has been shown to navigate through the peritoneal cavity of a mouse using magnetic control. The forward speed and drift speed of the ABF swarm are detected by following the centroid of the swarm area. The presence of proteins and endogenous biomacromolecules in the in vivo environment has an impact on the actuation speed and drive-in step-out frequency. It's worth noting that obtaining a suitable signal for tracking requires a large number of ABFs (8 104), implying that a swarming condition of microrobots might improve imaging contrast for microrobotic distribution. Imaging-guided distribution of biohybrid helical microrobots has been described, inspired by microalgae. (70) The robots are made by dipping them in Fe₃O₄ nanoparticle solutions with fluorescence inherited from *Spirulina*'s biological matrix. As a result, red-light fluorescence may be seen through green light emission without the need for fluorescence probes, allowing in vivo fluorescence imaging to monitor a group of microrobots. A magnetic needle is used to gather and steer the swarming biohybrid microrobots in the intraperitoneal cavity of mice in order to execute a controlled motion.

Radionuclide imaging techniques are extremely sensitive, allowing researchers to count the number of tagged micro/nanorobots at the whole-body level. The amount of radioactivity released is related to the number of labeled species present. (149–151) Incorporating positron or gamma emitters into microrobots might be an appropriate method for tracking microswarms in vivo using nuclear imaging techniques such as positron emission tomography (PET) or

single-photon emission computed tomography (SPECT) (SPECT). Exogenous agents-radionuclides, which directly emit and indirectly produce rays in the positron-electron annihilation process in SPECT and PET, respectively, are involved in the imaging mechanism. The rays' great penetrating ability decreases the effect of tissue attenuation even further. These imaging techniques are commonly employed in conjunction with anatomical techniques such as computed tomography since they provide insufficient morphological information (CT). In clinical settings, PET and SPECT, in conjunction with CT, are frequently used. They are used to make early diagnoses and assess patient reactions to treatment for a variety of illnesses. Vilela et al. have demonstrated that radio-labeling on the layer of microrobots allows for PET-CT monitoring. (131) Iodine-124 is labeled throughout the synthesis. PET can visualize the motions of a swarm of these microrobots in a phantom, indicating that functionalized microswarms might be located in vivo. Furthermore, swarming tagged microagents can monitor the activity of biological processes by providing dynamic quantitative information on the temporal evolution of their geographical distribution. The temporal resolution of PET is one of its primary drawbacks. Seven frames were collected throughout the course of 15 minutes of imaging in this study.

In radiology, MRI is used to create images of the anatomy and physiological processes of the body. Without exposing the body to radiation, it is frequently used for medical diagnosis, illness staging, and follow-up. In the field of microrobotics, MRI scanners are even being investigated as a possible assisting tool for navigation control in vascular networks.(152) Although MRI is incompatible with magnetic actuation systems, microswarm tracking and control may be done in other ways, or the gradient coil can be used for magnetic actuation. (153) Both natural and artificial microrobots have been delivered using MRI guidance. Using MRI, a swarm of biotemplate magnetite microrobots is in vivo localized in the stomachs of rats, with the swarm's navigation and imaging alternating. (70) In MR images, susceptibility artifacts adjacent to the subcutaneous tissue are shown, suggesting the presence of a high-concentration area of magnetic agents driven by a rotating magnetic field (magnetic swarm). Martel et al. looked at using an MRI-integrated platform to magnetically direct bacteria through the microvasculature. (154,155) The polar magnetotactic bacterial robot displays cargo manipulation under MRI feedback, illustrating the possible uses of MRI-guided steerable bacteria swarms. Magnetic particle imaging is another magnetic field-based imaging method (MPI). Unlike MRI, MPI focuses on paramagnetic substances (such as magnetic nanoparticles) rather than tissue. A selection field outside a central field-free zone, known as a field-free point (FFP) or field-free line, is used to excite paramagnetic particles (FFL). Shifting the FFP or FFL over an imaging volume produces an image. The particle magnetization responds nonlinearly throughout the excitation process. The magnetization signal's harmonics cause a voltage in the receiver coil, and the location of particles is linked to FFP. (156) The voltages in the field-free zone are directly proportional to the particle concentration, allowing for quantitative measurement. As a result, MPI is an effective imaging method for locating magnetic nanoparticle swarms. Recent investigations have demonstrated MPI-guided magnetic hyperthermia (120) and selective control of magnetic agents, in addition to imaging. (157) Active delivery in biological applications will benefit from further research into MPI-integrated particle swarm localisation.

It's worth noting that photoacoustic imaging has recently gotten a lot of interest from academics. The photoacoustic effect, in which laser pulses delivered into biological tissues are absorbed and transformed into heat, resulting in transitory thermoelastic expansion and wide-band (MHz) ultrasonic emission, underpins this imaging approach. Ultrasonic transducers detect and produce ultrasonic waves, which are subsequently processed to produce pictures. Photoacoustic imaging can be utilized for biological sensing since optical absorption is strongly related to physiological characteristics like hemoglobin content and oxygen saturation. Label-free imaging of single flowing red blood cells supplying oxygen to tissue, for example, may be achieved (158), as well as the whole-body dynamics of small animals. (159) A recent study (129) shows that a photoacoustic imaging-guided system can deliver swarming microrobots in the intestines *in vivo*, implying that the combination of control and imaging systems allows for deep imaging and accurate control of a small-scale swarm in a living organism. A swarm of polydopamine (PDA)-coated magnetic microrobots displays regulated translational motion in the subcutaneous tissues of mice, as shown in photoacoustic pictures. The photoacoustic signal and photothermal impact are enhanced by the PDA coating, allowing for imaging-guided photothermal treatment. The microrobots' swarming improves the contrast in the subcutaneous location, and the swarm's movement can be easily followed. The current findings suggest that photoacoustic imaging might be used to identify interactions between microrobots and biological tissue.

Summary

Microrobotic swarms and their applications in robotic delivery have advanced significantly during the last decade. We looked at the latest advancements in microrobotic swarm formation, navigation, and localization, as well as their applications in imaging-guided targeted delivery. While considerable work has been suggested in the direction of *in vivo* controlled delivery, numerous constraints remain, and much development in directing microrobotic swarms to achieve specific delivery tasks is required. In this respect, the research prospects and difficulties are described as follows, with prospective remedies on the horizon, as we perceive them to be. 3D Navigation, Long-Range Delivery, and Environmental Adaptability in Swarm Control *In Vivo*

Swarm control differs from single-robot control or multirobot operation in terms of control logic. The control algorithm must take into account the pace of access, the interaction between swarms and surroundings, and even statistical feedback. (160) I Navigation in three dimensions. Most existing collective micro/nanorobots are restricted to 2D space (near a substrate or border), but complicated 3D delivery tasks need 3D navigation. This type of navigation necessitates gravity/buoyancy force correction as well as a reliable control system that allows for multidimensional feedback information processing. To aid the control process, environmental boundaries should be reviewed.

One viable approach is to generate a 2D swarm followed by 3D navigation, but the constraints imposed by boundaries and the swarm's controllability must be reconsidered.(53,161) (ii) Delivery over a long period of time. Swarm control can be used in conjunction with current approaches such as catheter intervention. Swarm navigation across long distances takes time and puts a strain on the access rate of construction pieces (e.g., magnetic nanoparticles, mobile microorganisms). Before the catheter reaches a difficult-to-reach location, a swarm of micro/nano-objects can be placed into the tip and discharged, followed by guiding the swarm

via the constricted lumen to the target. The catheter, which is equipped with a mini-camera and sensors, may be utilized as an imaging tool for real-time environmental monitoring and haptic feedback. (162) The combination of aided tool navigation with robotic swarms provides an exciting research opportunity. (iii) Adaptability to the environment. The shape of constructed swarm patterns may be changed, allowing them to be used in restricted, dynamic settings. Excellent adaptability necessitates a quick reaction to external actuation energy, changeable morphology, and high pattern control repeatability. Integration of control systems, simultaneous localisation, and real-time environment registration are all required for swarm intelligence. Furthermore, a microrobotic swarm requires excellent locomotion in complicated fluids (e.g., blood, mucus) as well as the ability to navigate past biological obstacles (e.g., mucosal barrier, blood-brain barrier). (163–165) Control techniques for both overcoming biological barriers and sustaining a microrobotic swarm's functions must be investigated.

Microrobotic Swarm, Controller Unit, and Imaging Modality Integration

Integrating the swarm controller unit with in vivo imaging methods is a must for performing in vivo delivery jobs. Although various imaging techniques can be used to locate a microswarm inside opaque tissues or organs, the complexity of integrating imaging and control systems, as well as selecting the best imaging method based on navigation location, actuation method, building block materials, and delivery task, remain challenges. (169) Deep-tissue navigation is not possible with optical-based imaging. Ultrasound imaging, on the other hand, can penetrate deep tissue, but it's difficult to get enough image contrast in gas-filled body regions (e.g., lungs). The pattern creation and multidegree-of-freedom navigation of magnetically controlled microrobotic swarms are dependent on the size and bandwidth of the field generator (electromagnetic coils or permanent-magnet-based systems). (170) As a result, such controller units are not compatible with MRI systems. The trade-off between imaging and control systems, as well as the development of a swarm control scheme based on existing imaging systems, is very difficult to achieve.

Attention should be devoted to research into the integration of swarm navigation and imaging into the same energy source. The recent proposal for using MRI gradient coils to actuate small-scale robots suggests that such an integrated control/imaging system is a viable research area. (153) In order to create an imaging-integrated swarm control scheme, machine learning algorithms must be able to assess image input while also conducting adaptable swarm control. (171) The control technique might build a link between microrobotic swarms' collective behavior and biological surroundings in order to map physical limits and develop navigation strategies in complex situations. Deep neural networks, for example, may be used to evaluate medical picture feedback and track swarms. Then, swarm transformation control can be used to adapt to restricted surroundings.

Clinical Applications of a Microrobotic Swarm

Recent research has focused on combining robotic swarms with existing approaches (e.g., closed-loop control systems, medical imaging systems) for preclinical proof-of-principle trials. Before using microrobotic swarms in clinical applications, such as imaging-guided treatment, numerous difficulties must be addressed. First and foremost, efforts should be focused on system integration, which includes hardware, software, and autonomous control. Several current techniques, including catheters and endoscopes, can be combined to help with delivery and treatment operations. (172,173) User interfaces that incorporate both microrobotic control

and feedback processing systems are necessary to control microswarms in vivo in real time and monitor the treatment operation. Autonomous control allows for great manipulation efficiency and relieves medical practitioners of repetitive, time-consuming tasks. However, the degree of autonomy must be debated, as fully automated systems need extensive coding and may pose a safety risk. Second, in order to carry out targeted therapy, safety problems such as the effective dose of administration (pharmacokinetics), the dependability of integrated systems, and the penetration of biological barriers should be considered. (174,175) Before creating treatment methods, the biocompatibility and toxicity of swarms should be assessed. Recent research, including hydrogel micro/nanoparticles and hydrogel-based micro/nanostructures, has demonstrated the biocompatibility and biomedical uses of hydrogels. (176,177) These small hydrogel-based compounds can be used as building blocks to reduce microswarm toxicity. Biohybrid agents, such as particles contained in the plasma membrane of human platelets, cell membrane-coated micro/nanorobots, and biohybrid microrobots, can also improve a swarm's biocompatibility. (178–180) The toxicity threshold required varies depending on where microrobotic swarms are used. To determine if the swarm is biocompatible and safe for oral administration, histological examination of the toxicity of the swarm is performed on the stomach, duodenum, jejunum, distal colon, and ileum following the delivery process in the gastrointestinal system of live mice. (127,129)

Swarms in endovascular delivery applications may necessitate a more thorough toxicity assessment that considers a variety of factors such as materials, dosage, and building block size. Ex vivo experiments and animal testing must be carried out to determine the viability of the suggested system, which will need the participation of roboticists, material experts, and medical practitioners. Third, developing a game-changing application to aid medical practitioners and collaborators in assessing the methods for employing microrobotic swarms for focused therapy. More medical practitioners may be drawn to employing microrobotic swarms in focused diagnosis and therapy as a result of the collected experience. Imaging-guided treatment is the ultimate application aim of active-delivered microrobotic swarms. Swarming microrobots in imaging-guided treatment currently have limited proof-of-concept and in vivo research. Imaging-integrated swarm control methods focus more on swarm localization and navigation, whereas medical imaging systems have yet to be widely used in targeted treatment applications. For clinical applications, there are research possibilities for bridging tailored therapy/delivery and imaging-guided swarm control.

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